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Does gender-sensitive teacher training have a place in Engineering Education?

Assessing pedagogical training as a step towards gender-inclusive curricula

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INTRODUCTION

Inclusive teaching strategies aim to foster learning for all students. Traditionally, in the literature on gender and teaching, a special focus is given to strategies that may lead to include or to exclude female and male students.

Teaching advisors seek to sensitize teachers to use inclusive teaching pedagogies because they facilitate learning to all students. Being aware of gender-sensitive pedagogies may potentially lead

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teachers to consider how to manage better the gender composition of a class with respect to teaching strategies and interactions. A failure to do so has been shown to create learning environments which can hamper female students' learning and their decision to continue to pursue a career in Engineering.

This paper presents the results of a self-assessment of our teacher education activities. These are mostly short workshops and some longer courses. Four teaching advisors were involved in this project.

The aims of the study was to identify how the teaching training offered by our unit sets the example for gender sensitive teaching to its participants. In order to reach this aim, we assessed the materials and the learning activities used in our workshops from a gender approach.

A checklist for self-assessing our practice was developed by our team. This checklist was inspired on two research-based tools for gender in teaching. The checklist made the team reflect on things we perhaps did not normally consider. Because of responding to it, we identified what further research needs to be done in order to address some gender related issues. This checklist is presented here as a useful reflective tool for trainers.

Our results show that as a team, we have a clear intention to challenge gender bias in teaching and in responding to the checklist opened a discussion on our views and practices towards gender-sensitive teacher education. This discussion is now a baseline towards the gender-inclusive teacher training we aspire to offer teachers in Engineering Sciences.

1 GENDER AND ENGINEERING EDUCATION

1.1 Background

Studying Engineering and Science seems a constant fight for women, since their first day on campus.

Institutional efforts to value women in science and engineering abound, but they can have an adverse effect to their noble intention to help. A longitudinal study on students' intake of Women in Engineering Programs (WIE) reports that women shy away from studies after feeling 'spotlighted' for being women, instead of feeling encouraged for their competencies and knowledge like the rest of students. They conclude that in singling out female students a feeling of discomfort arises, either by promoting studies in engineering to young girls or by integrating female students to mentoring programs once at university. This is called spotlighting [1] and, in terms of gender inclusion for learning, spotlighting could be avoided with other strategies such as the pedagogy in the classroom.

Some learning strategies that that can be gender inclusive are design thinking and problem-based learning, notably because in engineering education studies have shown that the distribution of tasks within working groups have a gender dimension which can be addressed. For instance, a panel of experts in 2015 [2] discussed how women's' persistence to stay in engineering is associated to group work performance where girls often do the scheduling of meetings and organizing of final reports and are often excluded from the mathematical problem solving tasks.

Likewise, accounts of interactivity during team projects report that women are interrupted more frequently when they speak and have their design proposals underplayed [3]. A similar qualitative study also found that within student groups, the academic and seniority status of students affected group dynamics more directly than gender biases [4]. Both of these studies argue that despite other factors affecting group dynamics more negatively than gender, the cumulative, long-term effect of undervaluing women becomes a serious obstacle for women in developing a sense of engineering expertise.

Because male and female scientists carry gender biases into their professional practice, it is important to encourage gender sensitive epistemology to future scientist. For instance, Handley

etals, (2015) [5] concluded that what affects scientists' reactions to research on gender in science is not the quality of science that is reported but the reference to gender in the scientific papers.

The evidence presented above raises the question of finding what Karen Tonso proposes as 'insightful pedagogical practices' [in 3, pp.247] which would help to evaporate a learned indifference to gender inequalities instilled in the early years of studies, enforced throughout the academic years and later reproduced in professional practice.

1.2 Gender-sensitive pedagogies

Gender sensitive pedagogies are those instructional methods which allow students to participate equally and enables them to learn, regardless their gender. An example is peer instruction: Zhang, Ding and Mazur [6] showed that when taught with peer-instruction, first year students shift attitudes towards learning physics, they also found that female students speak more during peer-instruction than during bigger group unstructured discussion, typical of a lecture.

We adhere to the principle that gender sensitive pedagogies foster better learning because they boost constructive interaction between students. The research done by Chi, M. (2009) [7] shows how interactive instruction increases student learning by stimulating constructive dialogue and equal participation.

Therefore we will discuss some of the instructional methods that we consider adequate when training Science and Engineering instructors to teach. The paper also discusses the challenges that this initiative imposes on educational developers.

1.3 The challenge for teacher training

Studies on gender in teacher education argue that because teachers and scientists' are exposed to implicit gender biases during their pedagogical training, teachers later on reproduce them in their professional practice.

These studies raise the question of whether teaching education in Engineering promotes gender-sensitivity or reinforces gender biases.

It is believed that implicit gender biases in the materials used for teacher training reinforce the masculine culture of Engineering Education. For example, Zittleman & Sadker, [8] took a close look at teacher education textbooks and identified a series of sources for gender biases. The list highlights a superficial presentation of gender prejudice as well as of homophobia and harassment in the textbooks. Other sources of biases include the choice of textbook images and the choice of cited authors of which three out of four are male. Their main concern is that once in the classroom, teachers would implicitly reproduce such biases.

According John Hattie's meta-analysis, exemplary teacher education underlines good teaching that boosts learning. He identified three main characteristics of good teaching in Higher Education: having clear goals, using different interactive and inclusive teaching strategies and giving and getting feedback on teaching, all of which can be taught to pre-service teachers [9]. As described by Darling-Hammond, what makes teacher education exemplary is: a coherent vision of good teaching, an accountability to standards of good practice and, most importantly to this paper, an education which confronts teachers with their prior beliefs and assumptions about learning (in [10], page 113). Following this line of argument, teacher training opportunities that challenge teachers' prior beliefs, about gender and learning, would require the use of gender-sensitive pedagogies.

Therefore, the motivation of our study was to identify the gender-sensitive pedagogies used in our teacher training workshops and alternatively adjust the workshops in order to include gender sensitive teaching strategies in their delivery.

1.4 Aim of this paper

The main question of this paper was to identify *what* gender-sensitive pedagogies are used in our teaching training opportunities targeted to teachers in Higher Education science, technology engineering and mathematics (STEM).

Other questions that became relevant are: Do we identify implicit gender biases in the planning, organising and delivery of our workshops, and if yes, what can we do to eliminate these? Which areas of the training activities at our unit are more prone to use gender-sensitive pedagogies? What changes to make in support of our initiative but without spotlighting the underrepresented?

In order to respond to these questions, the paper draws on previous research and on European initiatives to structure gender-inclusive curricula.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 A checklist

A first step was to define an instrument to help assess our approach to gender in teaching training. The GARCIA project toolkit for Developing Gender gender-sensitive curricula [11] and the self-evaluation checklist built by the e-equal project, University of Fribourg [12] were our sources of inspiration. Both tools are evidence-based and built to support trainers in designing program and courses from a gender-inclusive perspective. The GARCIA project gives recommendations such as reflecting on how many female/ male academics one invites for visiting lectures. It also suggest finding examples that are renowned for their gender-sensitive approaches. These checklists are a first step to a reflection and analysis of text and images, course content and examples but also of the type of learning activities and student evaluation methods.

In addition, our checklist has sections that we found would help us contextualise our training in Science and Engineering education; such developing the critical thinking of the participants with regards to gender in teaching. We also found it important to include a possibility for peer assessment, and therefore the checklist also includes an observation grid.

The self-assessment checklist is divided in two parts. The questions are fully presented later on in the results tables. Part I, with 6 questions the intentions and aims of the workshop, of which an extract is presented in Table 1 below. Part II, with 8 questions asks for the content of the material and the learning activities used in the workshops. An observation for peer-assessment completes the checklist but is not reported here.

Table 1. An extract of Part I of the checklist.

Intentions and objectives Before the workshop	yes	No	Get info.	Irrele vant	Evidence / comment
1. Do you prepare your participants to be gender-sensitive teachers?					
2. Have you included in the readings gender-sensitive publications?					
3. Have you devoted at least some time to gender dimension of the workshop subject?					

4. Do you plan to make your participants more aware about gender stereotypes connected to the topic of the workshop?					
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2.2 Self-assessment

Each teaching advisor completed a self-assessment for each workshop they already facilitate. After each trainer responded, they were invited to discuss their reflections of doing the self-assessment with the project leader and later all together in a seminar-type session.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Four Teaching Advisors self-evaluated 14 workshops of which 9 are offered exclusively to Professors (Full, tenured and tenure-track), 4 to PhD Assistants and 2 to Bachelor and Master students. Post-Docs are welcome to attend any workshop. The total of 17 answers show that we take turns in facilitating the PhD workshops throughout the year. The quantitative data is shown below.

The tables below show the frequency analysis for the responses per question and it groups all workshops. Five replies were possible: 'yes', 'no', 'irrelevant' and 'get information' it was also possible to leave the space without an answer. Fig 1. shows the results for Part I of the checklist: the intentions and preparation of the workshop including the design and planning of each workshop asking about the content, the material and the teaching strategies planned for the event. Fig. 2 below shows the results for the self-assessment of the content (concepts, examples illustrations) and materials (images, slides, objects) for the workshops and courses.

The histograms shown below shows the results for self-assessing the design and planning of workshops. Questions ask for the content, the material and the teaching strategies planned for the event.

Figure 1: Self-assessment of planning (i.e. intentions, aims, choice of material)
14 responses

Figure 2: Self-assessment of material (text, theory, images)
14 responses

Results show that the material used for training teachers is gender neutral in text and images, using the English gender-neutral 'it / the', or taking images and pictures respective of gender equality or by not using human images. Almost all workshops aim for critical thinking but only in three of them, the workshop activities intend for discussing gender biases or reflect on inequality.

In general, teacher training is organised thinking to be gender-inclusive. Our results show the use of gender-sensitive pedagogy for certain workshops that can potentially be used in other workshops. These were the think-pair-share, jigsaw activities and electronic voting.

Some content addresses gender in learning such as in problem solving, where differences between girls and boys are shown as well as of gender stereotypes in study habits. Gender and fairness is presented when speaking about evaluating student learning, as reliability can contain gender bias.

Our results showed a positive predisposition to learn more about gender assumptions in solving engineering-type problems, carrying out group work as well as in avoiding spotlighting and gender stereotypes in workshops practicing presentations skills in teaching. More research is needed on information on gender stereotypes and hierarchies in relevant domains of teaching.

Trainers know something about gender-sensitive teaching methodology but still wish to know more. Generally we are all willing to prepare teachers to be gender sensitive instructors. While the highest positive response is on the intention to raise awareness of gender stereotypes, the lowest positive response is about including the development of gender competencies as an objective of workshops. Five workshops include material with reference to gender. Six workshops deal with the gender dimension of certain subjects linked to teaching and learning.

Concisely, the results confirm a systematic use of gender neutral written and audio-visual supports. We found an overall positive attitude to learn more about the gender dimensions of teaching and of gender sensitive pedagogies. This shared intention to educate teachers to become gender sensitive teachers has led to apply more widely think-pair-share and the electronic voting as gender-sensitive teaching methods.

4. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The answer to our main question is: mostly yes. Yes, we are preparing teachers to be gender-sensitive teachers by carefully planning our workshops and choosing relevant research and examples in the content and the material. However, the self-evaluation showed that we needed to take a closer look at our individual insights to gender-sensitive pedagogies in order to share them and use them.

Did we identify implicit gender biases in our practices as teacher trainers? Mostly no, but if some were identified in the choice of images have already undergone revision. Nevertheless, this point deserves to dig deeper into our choice of content, examples that may build bridges between gender and teaching the in STEM disciplines.

Do we use gender-sensitive pedagogies, and are these more adequate to some trainings? Yes, we use gender-sensitive pedagogies, and they might apply to all workshops. Our results confirm that we use interactive teaching strategies such as the think-pair-share consequently we, as a team, have discussed how to balance classroom participation. We have since identified research relevant to our aspirations and teaching practices, such as electronic voting for peer-instruction looking at gender [13].

We feel we have learnt from this project and are enthusiastic about the next steps. There is still some way to go: for example, when presenting these approaches to teachers do we call them gender-sensitive or just 'good teaching'? How do we raise awareness of gender issues in classrooms but avoid spotlighting? These are questions that we will want to address.

A few last words on the checklist, which we built based on existent ones: we found it extremely useful as a reflective tool. Let me explain; the individual questioning of our practices and the common sharing of results opened a space for us to discuss the experience as respondents to the checklist and it got conversation going on sensitive issues and teacher training. This has been unanimously a rewarding learning experience. The reflexivity ignited by this exercises is still alive. We find it would be a positive result to apply it in other contexts and training programs.

We expect to keep the enthusiasm in training teachers and we shall insist on the importance of gender-sensitive teaching in an Engineering and Science curricula.

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